

Family is the center of moral education**Hasanova Madina Saidovna –**

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Abstract: Family is a social unit based on natural-biological, economic, spiritual relations, it is a space that creates comfortable conditions for human life and satisfies his various needs.

Key words: Family, pedagogy, natural-biological, economic, spiritual life, national, tradition, human, social.

Аннотация: Семья — это социальная ячейка, основанная на естественно-биологических, экономических, духовных отношениях, пространстве, создающая комфортные условия для человека и удовлетворяющая разнообразные потребности его личности.

Ключевые слова: Семья, педагогика, эстетико-биологическое, экономическое, духовная жизнь, национальный, традиция, человеческий, социальный.

The family is the main and initial level of society, the first forms of the first union formed by mankind were "family", i.e. "ahle bayt" (women). The communities of Ahl al-Bayt gradually developed and became a community and a tribe" (48,13) . So, the initial stage of community life begins with the structure of the family, a person feels happy with a small union family in the bosom of a large community.

Family is a social unit based on natural-biological, economic, and spiritual relations, and it is a space that creates comfortable conditions for human living and satisfies his various needs.

Also, the family is a place of education that ensures life and the continuity of generations, preserves sacred traditions and conveys them to future generations, and directly affects how future generations will grow up to be human beings. It is an institution with a social and educational value, which ensures mutual equality of family members, mutual understanding, continuity of generations, educates them economically, spiritually, morally, physically, and aesthetically.

In particular, to carefully preserve the national traditions, life-giving customs and traditions of the family, integrate them with universal human values, protect motherhood and childhood, and provide all-round assistance to the family in fulfilling its sacred task of raising a well-rounded generation. By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers, it was entrusted to the scientific-practical center "Family".

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, IAKarimov, emphasized the importance of family education in raising a mature generation and said: "The main task is to steadily build a populist and just society in the republic. A hardworking and wealthy, spiritually mature and cultured family is the foundation of society."

In the anthology of Uzbek pedagogy, "achieving the education of the young generation on the basis of folklore, as well as national and universal qualities expressed in our ancient values", as well as "... the etiquette of folk oral creativity, its educational and educational aspects in our daily life to be able to use more than ever - the requirements of our time, our independence.

The importance of the family in the life of the society has been emphasized by the Uzbek people since ancient times.

Nizamul Muluk expresses the opinion that the society should take responsibility for raising children. So he paid special attention to the social importance of education. It shows the role of relatives and neighborhood people in the upbringing of a child.

The holy book of Zoroastrianism, "Avesta", glorifies a person who earns an honest living thanks to work, and it is emphasized that only the head of the family who loves the land can provide for his family. In this sacred work, the problem of protecting the family is highlighted. The idea of rewarding women who have given birth to and raised several children, and assigning allowances has been put forward.

In Islamic values, special importance is attached to raising a child in the family as a person worthy of society, moral, hardworking, and possessor of beautiful virtues. In particular, the hadith of Muhammad, peace be upon him: "A father cannot leave a legacy to his child more than morals", it is emphasized that the most important aspect of family education is the gift of morals to the child.

There are many examples in history of the fact that many famous people were born to mothers, their knowledge, knowledge of folklore and the fact that they passed it on to their children. Beruni attaches special importance to the place of a woman in the family. He says that the main reason for family stability is due to a woman who respects her husband, is neat and clean, and in order. It is known that a healthy lifestyle is a broad concept, which includes productive work, active rest, regular sports, physical exercise, personal, professional and psychohygiene. It is expressed in eating, refraining from harmful habits, going through an annual medical examination and forming a healthy family. Also, a healthy lifestyle is reflected in a person's skills related to forming a healthy family and having healthy children. Today in higher education, the formation of knowledge, skills, and reproductive culture in meeting the requirements of intellectual, professional, moral, and cultural development of students is considered to be the main part of educational goals, especially the pedagogical profession. in experts within.

At the current stage of human development, while the achievements of scientific and technical development are being widely used, there is an increase in the number of maternal illnesses, child deaths, the number of weak and disabled children born, the spread of various viral diseases, and the deterioration of the health of mothers and children. To pay special attention to immediate family issues, the health of mothers and children, the issue of the birth of healthy children from healthy mothers, as well as the comprehensive preparation of young people for family life before they even start a family, as well as the birth of children in the family and thus requires timely and high-level scientific knowledge of related issues.

This evidence presented on health problems proves that the perception of a person about a healthy lifestyle, the level of literacy is the main factor in the growth and maturity of a person.

In medical encyclopedias, the concept of health is explained and studied in 4 main directions.

1. Health by status. This direction determines the general state of the organism, determines its biological growth and development process.
2. Health on the move. This direction determines the level of growth, ensuring the movement tasks of various organs of the human body.
3. Mental health. This term was introduced to science in 1979 and defines the human mental state. It studies the mental state of a person, i.e. joys and worries, various changes, events on health based on their natural and social possibilities.

4. Spiritual health. This is the ability of a person to find his place in society, to regulate his own behavior and inner experiences, to be loyal to universal values and to use them in establishing a way of life, to choose a rational way in difficult life situations. determined by formation. Some Russian scientists, for example, T.F.Akbashev , BAKlassov, complement the spiritual health of a person in a unit of three factors, that is, social, intellectual and reproductive health.

According to them, intellectual health is reflected in thinking, receiving information and conveying it, while social health is reflected in a person's social activity, finding his place in society, and professional maturity. Reproductive health is manifested in relationships with parents, family relationships, sexual culture, having children and raising them.

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